

The performance of vocational high school principal's learning supervision in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

Supervision of learning is one of the most important parts of improving the quality of education. It is necessary to develop an evaluation instrument that can assess the performance of school principals' learning supervision, to achieve national education goals that accord the needs of the times. So, the purpose of this study is to produce an instrument for assessing the learning supervision performance of the head of vocational high school (VHS) that can be used as a reference for supervisors. The method used is research and development (R&D) with a 4D model defined, designed, developed, and disseminated. The research subjects involved 20 school supervisors, 218 principals, and 314 teachers. Data collection techniques employed interviews, questionnaires, and documentation. Data analysis used the qualitative analysis techniques (interviews) and quantitative analysis (statistics). The results showed that this assessment instrument is an excellent category with an average score of 4.21. This assessment consists of three assessor components: school supervisors, teachers, and school principals. This assessment instrument can be the latest guideline for supervisors who will evaluate the performance of school principals and teachers, so the evaluation carried out is effective, efficient, and optimal in improving the quality of education.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Education has a strategic function in developing dignified character and personality in the intellectual life of the nation [1]–[8]. Vocational high school (VHS) is an education that prepares students, mainly so that graduates are ready to work according to their competencies in the industrial world [9]–[13]. Furthermore, equipping students with competencies through the selected skill program [14], [15]. In practice, the implementation of education shows that there is a gap between *das sein* and *das sollen*. “*Das sein*” refers to the current state of affairs or reality, while “*das sollen*” represents an ideal or desired state that should be achieved through actions and efforts. This discrepancy between *das sein* and *das sollen* highlights the need for educational reform to address the issues that hinder the realization of the desired educational outcomes. The current phenomenon of education is that there are still many educational programs whose success rates have not been measured. Because it was not evaluated professionally, the effectiveness and efficiency of the program are unknown [16]–[18].

The principal is a determinant of the management of school education and improving the quality of education at the school level [19]–[21]. In addition to the principal having a strategic role in improving teacher professionalism and the quality of education, he or she must also provide guidance, direction, encouragement, motivation, and inspiration to teachers, staff, and students to achieve school goals [22]–[24]. Therefore, the managerial and academic work functions of school principals need special attention, especially regarding performance in their implementation.

The principal has personality and social competencies, learning leadership, school development, resource management, entrepreneurship, supervision, appearance, service, and achievement, as well as the implementation of culture-based education [25], [26]. But in fact, several research results show that the implementation of VHS still shows weaknesses in various aspects, one of which is in the aspect of the principal's managerial and academic duties. The results are supported by the results of the principal competency test by the Directorate General of Quality Improvement of Educators and Educational Personal or Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology (Kemendiknas) in Indonesia with the results that around 70% of 250 thousand school principals in Indonesia are incompetent, and surprisingly it was revealed that the mastery of the managerial competence of principals in 2019 only reached <50% [27]. This is the basis that the performance of VHS principals needs serious attention from various parties, both stakeholders, and policymakers [28], [29].

Previous studies [24], [30], [31] also found several issues regarding the problem of evaluating the performance of school principals such as the limited involvement of teachers in the managerial and academic performance appraisal of the principal of VHS, the role of the principal is not yet optimal. School supervisors in assessing the managerial and academic performance of VHS principals, there is still limited guidance for school principals by the education office to improve VHS performance, and there is still limited involvement of the community and school committees in improving the performance of school principals. These various limitations are, of course, problems that need to be resolved, so as not to become a ticking time bomb that further worsens the quality of national education. Therefore, the implementation of the managerial and academic performance evaluation management model as one of the important components of VHS is very necessary. The ideal principal is a principal who can carry out management functions well [25], [30]–[32].

Conceptually management is an activity to guide people to work or do what is needed to achieve a goal [33], [34]. The functions of education management from a schooling perspective include planning, organizing, implementing, and supervising [35]–[37]. The content of this research, and planning activities contain activities to formulate goals, set and interpret evaluation management, prepare budgets, and develop standards. Organizing contains activities to develop an organizational structure, delegate authority and responsibility, establish procedures for using resources, design work, and develop job descriptions. Directing contains activities to motivate, train and develop subordinates, develop communication channels, and assess personnel leadership styles. Controlling contains activities to evaluate the results of the evaluation activities, take corrective action on the evaluation results, conduct performance appraisals, report results, and monitor activities on an ongoing basis.

Currently, the evaluation management process used by various educational institutions still uses conventional management models and is not based on research and development [34], [38]. Evaluation management continues to evolve from simple to complex processes. Most conventional evaluation management only uses three steps, namely program design, program implementation, and program results reports [37], [39], [40]. This study assesses the implementation of a more complete, complex, and accountable evaluation management model that includes the functions of organizing, monitoring, and evaluating the implementation of activities. So far, evaluation activities have focused more on assessment activities, such as the Principal Performance Assessment (PKKS) which has not been well managed and organized. The result is that the principal's performance report card is incomplete, making it difficult to follow up, especially since the principal does not receive the report card.

Managerial and academic performance are two performance variables that must be owned by school principals [26], [41]. In this conception, Yuliana, Sugiyono, and Prasojo [27] explained that the principal's managerial performance includes his ability to plan, develop organizations as needed, manage change, create a school climate and culture, and manage teachers, staff, and students, manage facilities, infrastructure, and take advantage of technological advances to improve learning and school management. Meanwhile, the principal's academic performance includes the ability to develop a curriculum, develop academic documents, develop information and communication technology (ICT) models, plan academic supervision programs, and carry out academic supervision [20], [24], [42]. These two areas are the focus of the discussion of this research, especially regarding the performance of school principals in the managerial and academic fields.

Management assessment of the managerial and academic performance of the principal of VHS is important to do to obtain a model that is empirically tested for effectiveness, efficiency, and practicality. The evaluation management model that has been empirically tested is expected to have high sustainability to be carried out in the following years [26], [27], [34]. In addition, if evaluation management is successfully

implemented, it is hoped that it will be applied to other similar programs (transferability). Therefore, it is urgent to assess whether the managerial and academic performance evaluation of the principal of VHS is valid, credible, and accountable. The reason for VHS as a research subject is interesting because as a vocational institution it contributes to the success of the implementation of national education. In addition, research conducted among vocational high schools regarding the performance of school principals is still relatively small.

Management assessment of the principal's managerial and academic performance evaluation becomes very important with various theoretical and empirical considerations [22], [28]. The assessment system is not controlled by a management model so starting from time planning, organizing, implementation, and monitoring, to the sustainability process as post-evaluation feedback is not well-systemized [33], [37], [39], [40], [43]. Even the results of the assessment are not evaluated properly but the results are closed only for the consumption of the education office and secondary education centers. Meanwhile, the principal does not know how the performance value is, so performance improvement programs are not well directed. Therefore, it is necessary to assess a well-systematic management model in line with the management process theory, which is sourced from management philosophy, both ontologically, epistemologically, and axiologically. The new management model is an improvement model from PKKS whose instruments are the same as nationally centralized. In this study, the focus is on the performance of the principal as the leader of the education unit, not on the performance of the school institutionally.

The ability of the principal is very influential in improving the quality of managerial and academics which has an impact on the quality of the totality. If the principal carrying out his duties does not perform well, it will result in a low quality of the school, so that it will affect the image of the school and the image of education in general. The management of school principals' performance appraisals, which have been using PKKS, have not shown ideal management practices (*das sein*), so the management model developed now will be as expected (*das sollen*), which is effective, efficient, and has high practicability. Therefore, this study focused on assessing the managerial and academic performance evaluation management model of vocational high school principals by comparing centralized and collaborative management. The results of the study are expected to contribute to stakeholders, including the secondary education office, school supervisors, and school principals.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Research design

The research employed a research design and 4D model development [44]–[47], with the stages defined (needs analysis), designed (preparing a conceptual framework of models and instruments), developed (involving validity and feasibility tests against experts and limited trials), and disseminated (implementation on the target subject study) [44], [48]. The goal is to produce an instrument model for the assessment of the learning supervision performance of the principal of vocational high school (VHS). That is a product of the development of the existing model, namely the model for assessing the performance of the principal.

2.2. Research subject

The subject of research is the instrument for assessing the learning supervision performance of the head of the VHS. The object of this research is the principals and teachers of VHS in Yogyakarta, Indonesia who are used as observational units or can be said as experimental subjects. The data were obtained from superiors 218 principals, 314 competent teachers, and 20 supervisors.

2.3. Techniques and Instruments of data collection

Data collection techniques used a questionnaire. Test the validity of the data using triangulation of theoretical methods, data, and informant study [49]. From the initial data, it was compiled into a draft initial instrument, which was then tested qualitatively. After the product design and the selection of assessment categories have been completed, then the performance appraisal instrument is made, along with scoring and assessment rubrics to facilitate the assessment. Then the instrument was validated by experts and tested in the field. The field test was carried out in two stages (limited test and test was carried out on the expanded group). The assessment was carried out by researchers, by observing the results of the instrument trials filled out by superiors and teachers.

2.4. Data analysis technique

Qualitative analysis in this study is to analyze the validity of the content of the instrument developed and carried out by experts (expert judgment) [50]. The results of qualitative analysis are a requirement for conducting product trials, while quantitative data analysis uses statistics by looking at the characteristics of

the instrument, which consists of construct validity using factor analysis [51] and criterion validity using Pearson correlation values [52], [53]. The reliability of the instrument was tested using the Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient, with the help of version 26. The results of the validity and reliability test of the learning supervision performance instrument were Cronbach's alpha of 0.829 and the coefficient value was greater than 0.7 which means that it is reliable or reliable. The result of the alpha coefficient on this instrument is 0.8288, so that all items on the learning supervision performance instrument of the head of VHS are valid. Considering that this research is an evaluation study, the analysis uses evaluation criteria if the average score $x > 4.2$ is very good, $3.4 < x \leq 4.2$ is good, $2.4 < x \leq 3.4$ is moderate, $1.5 < x \leq 2.4$ is poor, and $x \leq 1.4$ is bad [54]. The average score of the instrument readability assessment shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The instrument readability assessment carried out by school supervisors, principals, and teachers

No	Assessed aspect	Average score
1.	Clarity of questionnaire instructions	4.63
2.	Instrument clarity	4.50
3.	Clarity of management steps	4.38
4.	Indicator clarity	4.13
5.	Clarity of implementation monitoring and evaluation aspects	4.13
6.	Standard Indonesian usage	3.88
7.	Easy-to-understand statement formulas	4.38
8.	Use of clear words and sentences	4.50
9.	Font shape and size	4.38
10.	Writing format	4.13
Total average score		4.30

The assessment of the user evaluators 10 shows that the overall average score is 4.30 or a very good category with a range of $>4.2-5.0$. The assessment explains that the instruments and items are appropriate or appropriate to measure the performance of the learning supervision of VHS principals in teacher management in Yogyakarta, Indonesia. Therefore, the research instrument is feasible and appropriate to use. The recapitulation of assessments by experts and users of the principal's assessment shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Recapitulation of assessments by experts and users of the principal's assessment

No	Assessed aspect	Average score
1.	Clarity of questionnaire instructions	3.93
2.	Instrument clarity	4.30
Total average score		4.12

3. RESULTS

Assessment instruments that have been declared feasible are ready to be used to assess the learning supervision performance of vocational high school principals in the management of teaching staff in Yogyakarta, Indonesia. To determine the performance of learning supervision using developed instruments, it is necessary to conduct a field study with ten supervisors from the local education and culture office. The assessment is carried out by providing an instrument for the learning supervision performance of the principal of VHS in the management of teachers which consists of 16 statement indicators. The assessment of learning supervision on the performance of the principal shown in Table 3.

The assessment of performance on the learning supervision of the principal of VHS in the management of teachers obtained an average score of 4.43. Thus, the learning supervision performance of VHS principals in teacher management based on the assessment of 20 school supervisors is included in the very good category based on a range of criteria >4.2 . All performance indicators in developing learning documents are included in the very good category. In addition to being assessed by the supervisor, the principal's performance was also assessed by the principal shown in Table 4.

The principal's assessment of the learning supervision performance of the principal of VHS in teaching management in Yogyakarta, Indonesia obtained an average score of 4.24. Thus, the learning supervision performance of VHS principals in the management of teaching staff based on the assessment of 218 principals is included in the very good category because it is on the criteria >4.2 . All performance indicators in developing learning documents are included in the very good category, except for indicators 1, 2, 3, 9, 10, and 14, each of which has an average score of 3.97 with a good category. In addition to being assessed by school supervisors and principals, the principal's performance is also assessed by teachers with the results presented shown in Table 5.

Table 3. The assessment of learning supervision on the performance of the principal

No.	Statement indicator	Average	Category
1.	Identifying learning needs	4.46	Very good
2.	Designing a learning supervision model	4.38	Very good
3.	Coordinate with school supervisors	4.15	Good
4.	Prepare general documents for learning supervision	4.31	Very good
5.	Develop supervision instruments	4.69	Very good
6.	Make a schedule for the implementation of supervision	4.62	Very good
7.	Coordinate with the vice-principal of the curriculum section	4.54	Very good
8.	Carry out learning supervision according to the schedule	4.85	Very good
9.	Assessing the teacher's ability to make lesson plans	4.23	Very good
10.	Assessing the ability of teachers in developing teaching materials	4.31	Very good
11.	Assessing the ability of teachers in making learning media	4.38	Very good
12.	Assessing the ability of teachers to apply innovative learning methods	4.46	Very good
13.	Evaluating learning activities	4.54	Very good
14.	Have a discussion with the teacher after the learning activity	4.00	Good
15.	Provide feedback to the teacher after carrying out the lesson	4.69	Very good
16.	Motivate teachers to make improvements to the planning and implementation of learning	4.31	Very good
Total average		4.43	Very good

Table 4. The results of the principal's evaluation of the principal's performance

No.	Statement indicator	Average	Category
1.	Identifying learning needs	4.00	Good
2.	Designing a learning supervision model	3.38	Good
3.	Coordinate with school supervisors	3.15	Good
4.	Prepare general documents for learning supervision	4.31	Very good
5.	Develop supervision instruments	4.66	Very good
6.	Make a schedule for the implementation of supervision	4.56	Very good
7.	Coordinate with the vice-principal of the curriculum section	4.33	Very good
8.	Carry out learning supervision according to the schedule	4.45	Very good
9.	Assessing the teacher's ability to make lesson plans	4.12	Good
10.	Assessing the ability of teachers in developing teaching materials	4.11	Good
11.	Assessing the ability of teachers in making learning media	4.34	Very good
12.	Assessing the ability of teachers to apply innovative learning methods	4.78	Very good
13.	Evaluating learning activities	4.87	Very good
14.	Have a discussion with the teacher after the learning activity	4.10	Good
15.	Provide feedback to the teacher after carrying out the lesson	4.36	Very good
16.	Motivate teachers to make improvements to the planning and implementation of learning	4.39	Very good
Total average		4.24	Very good

Table 5. The results of the teacher's assessment of the principal's performance

No.	Statement indicator	Average	Category
1.	Identifying learning needs	4.11	Good
2.	Designing a learning supervision model	4.14	Good
3.	Coordinate with school supervisors	4.19	Good
4.	Prepare general documents for learning supervision	3.87	Good
5.	Develop supervision instruments	3.76	Good
6.	Make a schedule for the implementation of supervision	4.16	Good
7.	Coordinate with the vice-principal of the curriculum section	3.13	Good
8.	Carry out learning supervision according to the schedule	3.67	Good
9.	Assessing the teacher's ability to make lesson plans	4.32	Very good
10.	Assessing the ability of teachers in developing teaching materials	3.14	Good
11.	Assessing the ability of teachers in making learning media	4.78	Very good
12.	Assessing the ability of teachers to apply innovative learning methods	3.68	Good
13.	Evaluating learning activities	4.67	Very good
14.	Have a discussion with the teacher after the learning activity	4.16	Good
15.	Provide feedback to the teacher after carrying out the lesson	3.52	Good
16.	Motivate teachers to make improvements to the planning and implementation of learning	4.15	Good
Total average		3.96	Good

The results of the teacher's assessment of the learning supervision performance of the vocational high school principal in the management of teachers in Yogyakarta, Indonesia is 3.96. The teachers' assessment of the learning supervision performance of the VHS principal in the management of teaching staff based on the evaluation of 314 teachers was included in a good category because they were on criteria >3.5–4.2. All performance indicators in the development of learning documents are included in the good category except indicators 9, 11, and 13 which get a score of 4.28. Thus, there is a difference between the

evaluation of school supervisors, teachers, and the principal's assessment of the performance of the learning supervision of VHS principals in teacher management. The results of the recapitulation of the three assessments are shown in Table 6.

Table 6. The recapitulation of the assessment of school supervision, principals, and teachers on the performance of school principals

No	Assessed aspect	Average score	Category
1.	School supervisions	4.43	Very good
2.	Principals	4.24	Very good
3.	Teachers	3.96	Good
Total average score		4.21	Very good

Interviews with several vocational schoolteachers in Yogyakarta, Indonesia that the principal's performance as a learning supervisor has not been running optimally due to the splitting of roles or duties of the principal himself so that the learning process carried out by the teacher is not monitored by the principal. This happened for two reasons, first, the principal failed to focus. The principal is too busy pursuing secondary targets and neglects the learning process. The inability of the principal to focus on the learning process will have a strong influence on the quality of the character of his students. Second, there is a feeling of reluctance or discomfort, which often arises when the principal is younger in age and experience than the teachers. This case is not uncommon. Principals lack sufficient confidence to supervise and provide an assessment of the performance of their teachers.

As a result of the non-optimal task of supervision, many schools stagnate and even live in a state of reluctance to die. The school runs like a robot. Just running a boring routine, without any innovation and creativity inspires the appetite to move forward and the passion to improve quality continuously. Of course, this will have a major impact on the cognitive development, skills, and attitudes of students [55].

The principal is the driving force in improving the quality of the school. The principal must view his teacher as the spearhead of the success of achieving the school's vision and mission. The principal must have the right perspective in making the spearhead and be sharp and hit the target when released [56]. This means that the principal will know very well the potential of his teachers so that he also knows what kind of coaching is needed by his teachers. Notes on the results of supervision become the capital of a school principal in preparing teacher development programs. The teacher development program is the responsibility of a school principal. Without the results of supervision, this teacher development program does not have a clear basis and direction. Unfortunately, many schools ignore this [57]. The school does not have a regular and well-planned teacher development program. The teacher training program is a benchmark for the quality of a school.

Educational units that want to continue to develop and improve their quality must have a continuous teacher development program to the demands of change and development of the times. The role of the principal is very important so he must carry out the task of supervising learning intensely and making notes of the results of his supervision as the basis for preparing teacher development programs in his school [58]. Thus, the expected improvement in the quality of education can be achieved following the established vision and mission.

4. DISCUSSION

The results of this study indicated that the assessments of school supervisors, principals, and teachers have provided a very good assessment of the performance of learning supervision with its capacity for program development and teacher development following the school's vision and mission. The learning supervision performance obtained an average score of 4.43 from the school supervisor. This explains that school supervisors have high confidence in the capacity of principals to manage programs relevant to teachers. School supervisors in several researches [59], [60] have made a significant contribution to improve school quality. Thus, school supervision that is considered good should be an important achievement among principals of vocational schools to receive input and suggestions in maintaining school quality.

The management model for evaluating the managerial and academic performance of vocational high school principals that has been running so far is the PKKS model which is carried out annually and every four years with the indicators assessed in the PKKS covering eight components, including i) Personality and social; ii) Learning leadership; iii) School development; iv) Resource management; v) Entrepreneurship; vi) Supervision; vii) Appearance, service, and achievement; and viii) Implementation of culture-based education. Personality and social aspects include indicators: i) Having noble character, developing a culture

and tradition of noble character, and being an example of noble character for the community in schools/madrasahs; ii) Carrying out the main duties and functions as a school principal with full honesty, sincerity, commitment, and integrity; iii) Being open in carrying out their main duties and functions as principals of schools/madrasahs; iv) Self-control in dealing with problems and challenges as principals of schools/madrasahs; v) Participate in social activities; vi) Responsive and concerned about the interests of other people or groups; vii) Develop and manage school/madrasah relationships with other parties outside the school to get ideas, learning resources, and school/madrasah financing. In PKKS, personality and social aspects are aspects that are assessed in evaluating the performance of school principals, while in the VHS school principal's learning supervision performance assessment model it is not included in the components that must be assessed considering that social and personality aspects must be good before the teacher is appointed as principal [61], [62].

There are several problems surrounding the previous assessment model, so it is necessary to develop a new model, namely the unmapped management model for the managerial and academic performance evaluation of VHS school principals in Indonesia that has been running so far. The model is very complicated and inefficient both in terms of time and implementation. The model is also not based on the work program of educational management which demands that all policies are based on management principles [63]. The management of the evaluation of the managerial and academic performance of the head of VHS found in the field by applying PKKS has not been optimal in assessing the performance of the principal effectively and efficiently. Some principals in VHS have an understanding that the principal's performance appraisal with the principal's performance evaluation is the same so that the assessment is the same as the evaluation. The principal's performance assessment aims to improve the principal's performance which refers to the school's vision and mission that has been prepared and agreed upon [64]–[66].

In the implementation of PKKS, especially in the implementation of the assessment, transparency is not optimal, there is no evaluation report for the principal, and too many assessors do not understand the real condition of the principal's performance such as student assessors, school committees, and parents so that the results of the assessment are less than optimal in capturing performance. Principal conditions like this hamper the data analysis process, especially when there is a lot of data that is of course biased [67]. As for other weaknesses, such as observational data which is not necessarily a real phenomenon, because the situation during the assessment may be different from the situation before the assessment [68], [69]. Therefore, integrated socialization is needed, and the assessment must be carried out in an objective, fair, transparent, and accountable manner [70], [71]. In addition, other weaknesses, and obstacles in the implementation of the existing managerial and academic performance evaluation management model for VHS principals are the lack of transparency of assessment results for principals so that the principals concerned do not know how their performance is for one year or two semesters.

Thus, various parties need to be understand the importance of assessing the performance of school principals, the results of which are not only to get the predicate very good or good [72], [73], but also objective results for improving the performance of school principals in the future through coaching by supervisors. Schools based on the results of performance evaluations. The best evaluation results are when the results are followed up by relevant parties such as school supervisors and school principals. The results of the performance evaluation are also useful for supervisors to carry out proper guidance on components and indicators of school principals' performance that are not yet optimal. Therefore, the coaching model will be by the real needs of improving the performance of the principal [74]–[76].

The learning supervision performance assessment model for the principal of VHS can be used as a diagnostic evaluation to find and map various aspects in detecting the principal's performance that needs to be improved. This model is open for further development such as development research using a structural model or with other constructive approaches. The characteristics of the model developed are based on objective, effective, and accountable principles so that they can explore the managerial and academic performance data of VHS school principals in a transparent and informative manner. Furthermore, this model involves various stakeholders, namely the education office, education center, supervisors, school principals, teachers, and education staff. The model also has innovative values, namely practicality in managing the evaluation of the managerial and academic performance of VHS principals and openness of results in the era of information disclosure.

5. CONCLUSION

The importance of using the vocational high school principal's learning supervision performance appraisal model by the education office in evaluating the managerial and academic performance of vocational high school principals as a representation of existing performance appraisals. The need for full support from stakeholders in the education authorities, school supervisors, principals, teachers, and education staff for the

implementation of the learning supervision performance assessment model for vocational high school principals so that programmatic socialization is needed. Furthermore, the need for full support from the principal in preparing supporting evidence for the implementation of the program objectively by the reality of the implementation of school programs, especially regarding the managerial and academic performance of the principal. The dissemination of research results can be carried out with the support of the education authorities which is directly related to the implementation process of existing models and new models that are more practical, effective, and efficient.

Although in general, the vocational high school principal's learning supervision performance appraisal model has advantages compared to other models, in the research process it has several limitations. It was the product of this research is intended to manage the managerial and academic performance evaluation of vocational high school principals, while for primary and secondary education it is necessary to conduct research continued development, given the characteristics of different schools. Dissemination of the assessment model needs to be carried out by involving a wider area based on its condition and stakeholders both at the education office, school supervisors, and other stakeholders.

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